

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT FOR WOMEN IN RURAL AREAS

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Abstract. *The article examines the problems of women's employment, analyzes the factors, proposes a number of measures of social mechanisms. Ways to increase the employment of rural women were also considered, and recommendations were made to improve the system of women's employment.*

Keywords: *women's employment, women's employment system, social mechanisms, demand and supply, family business, gender equality, labor relations, women's social activity, labor market, members of society.*

Today, when the composition of the resource potential of our country is studied, issues such as labor resources and ensuring their employment in various regions are said to be urgent. In the economy or state policy of developed countries, attention is paid to issues such as using the opportunities of regions far from the center as an important task. Including, special attention is paid to such industries in our country. In particular, some concepts are included in the legislation of the country. An important aspect of this is the gender composition of the country's labor resources.

In general, the majority of citizens in this segment of the country's population are young people and women. 49.7% of the population and 45% of labor resources are accounted for by women. So, most of the social issues in our country are closely related to their lives. In recent years, the issue of social protection of women, training them in professions and ensuring their employment has risen to the level of state policy, and a vertical system has been created in this regard, which is managed up to the neighborhood level. For women's issues, a separate deputy chairman was appointed in each neighborhood, a deputy head of the neighborhood and family department and 2 specialists in the district, and up to 8 staff units in the region.

On the initiative of the head of our state on October 8, 2020, at the meeting of video selectors to discuss measures to increase the role of women and youth in society and ensure employment, a new work system for women's issues was established - each neighborhood, district, "Women's register" was introduced in the city and region. Within the framework of the effectiveness of this system and the 5 important initiatives put forward by the President to raise the morale of young people and meaningfully organize their free time, important measures have been taken to provide employment for women [4]. In addition, according to the level of urbanization, the number of people living in the regions also varies. Urbanization is the process of increasing the role of cities in the development of society and economy, as well as the formation of urban infrastructure, which contributes to positive changes in the socio-professional and demographic structure of the population, and the quality of its lifestyle and culture to a new level.

Today, the employment rate of the country's population in Uzbekistan in January-September 2021 is 9.4%, which has decreased by 1.7% compared to the same period last year, and by 0.4% compared to January-June. This was stated in the notification of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations. In January-September 2021, the number of labor resources

amounted to 19.3 million people, which increased by 1.1 percent or 201.4 thousand people compared to the same period of 2020.

The number of people employed in economic sectors amounted to 13.6 million people, which increased by 3.1% compared to the corresponding period. In 9 months, the number of people employed in the official sector was 6.1 million people, and compared to the same period of 2020, the number of people employed in legal entities increased by 7.9 percent or 450.5 thousand people. The number of people employed in the informal sector amounted to 5.9 million people, which decreased by 4.1 percent or 254,000 people compared to January-June of this year. The total number of people in need of work was 1.4 million, the unemployment rate among the economically active population was 9.4 percent.

These indicators do not show the level of employment of the rural population. Therefore, some analyzes are being given. First, the territorial structure of the city's population will be internally enriched at the expense of this region and nearby regions. The reason for this is that the urban area has a lot of opportunities in terms of infrastructure and jobs. Secondly, it can be said that the level of industrialization of rural areas is high in some regions and low in some regions, that is, the distribution of resources does not correspond to the amount of jobs. Thirdly, the available jobs for residents of rural areas are mainly related to agricultural activities, which are considered to be seasonal in many ways. Fourthly, the rural population is characterized by a relatively fast increase, and there is a significant share of women and girls in the population.

Some conclusions can be drawn from the above practical indicators. Employment of the female population of the country increases the importance not only from the point of view of the city, but also from the point of view of using the available resources in the rural areas. In addition, it is possible to study the possibility of regions far from the centers and make some conclusions about the country's economy. There is also an economic importance of ensuring the employment of women in the society, which can be seen in the following.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy, it is necessary to strengthen the role of women, to eliminate obstacles to the improvement of their competitiveness in the rural labor market. If the main focus is on improving professional and professional skills, knowledge in the field of entrepreneurship in advance, it is possible to achieve elimination of obstacles through this.

Economic activity of women in Uzbekistan, as in the whole world, is lower than that of men. By the end of 2021, this figure was 41.3 percent for women and 56.9 percent for men. The economic activity of Uzbek women in the labor market begins at the age of 30. This is because, on average, she gets married at the age of 22.3 and then spends at least 2 years on maternity leave. After that, they return to the labor market, but after a short time, they are more likely to go on maternity leave again. In Uzbekistan, women mainly work in the public sector, which creates stable jobs and favorable conditions. The network structure of women's employment is characterized by the fact that they work mainly in areas with low wages and short working hours. These are sectors such as education, healthcare and the social sphere in general. This is the reason for the difference between men's and women's wages. As alternative solutions to this factor related to jobs, it is possible to highlight rural tourism and jobs for women created in it.

As evidence of our opinion, we can cite the conclusions of international experiences. At the current level of the Chinese economy, problems such as unemployment can also be observed, and at the same time, the opportunities of rural tourism and agrotourism are being used effectively as a solution to this.

Taking into account some of the analyzes presented above, several conclusions can be drawn. Let's say that the only solution for women's employment and providing them with work is not the state enterprises or organizations, but the farms themselves, which organize various family business and service sectors based on the economic potential of the regions. Moreover, through such activities, members of the society have the opportunity to raise their interests in any field, for example, crafts, weaving, cooking, handicrafts, and other activities to the level of the entire economy.

In our opinion, the consistent continuation of creative work in economic zones, small businesses and family facilities - new jobs at the expense of benefits, republican entrepreneurship - loans from commercial banks, production of exportable products in processing for the establishment of enterprises, industry, service sector and domestic foreign investments increase the efficiency of the financial and credit system and create new jobs.

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